

Time constraints on the geological evolution of the main sedimentary basins and tectono-magmatic events on Livingston Island, South Shetland Archipelago, Antarctica: a review

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Abstract. The Lower Cretaceous to Miocene South Shetlands Islands’ volcanic arc is a result of the subduction of the Phoenix Oceanic Microplate (part of the Pacific Plate) beneath the Antarctic Peninsula. The magmatic activity on Livingston Island has been going on for a long time: since the Early Cretaceous to the present. The evolution of the volcanic arc resulted in the formation of various sedimentary basins and paleoenvironments (turbiditic to shallow marine and continental) that formed varied sedimentary successions and tholeiitic to potassium calc-alkaline subduction-related magmatic rocks. Considering the magmatic activity on Livingston Island, a general trend of rejuvenation can be observed from the WNW (Byers Peninsula) to the ESE (to Hannah Point, Point Williams and further to the Hurd Peninsula and the Tangra Mountain). The rejuvenation of the magmatic rocks in the direction of the thrust plate can be explained as an effect of a flattening subduction that was active from the Early Cretaceous (135 Ma) up to around 90–70 Ma. The mixed ages of the dikes and small intrusions in the Hurd Peninsula are most probably due to periods of rotation and probably beginning of a slab-roll back. A regional Paleocene–Eocene (65–47 Ma) compressional episode that caused a low temperature to high-pressure metamorphism is registered on Smith and Elephant islands. The regional metamorphism was followed by a vast extension between 50–30 Ma that culminated with the opening of the Drake Passage around 34–30 Ma. The magmatic response of that regional scale extension was the intrusion of the Eocene Barnard Point Pluton (46–40 Ma) and dikes with youngest ages of around 30 Ma. The major uplift phase and the exhumation of the Tangra Mountain happened between 22–16 Ma as indicated by the Ap FT thermochronology. The last magmatic event on the island produced the contrastingly different in composition Quaternary alkaline mafic rocks that occupy the area between Innot Point and Burdick Peak. This episode is interpreted as related to a process of crustal extension that culminated in asthenospheric upwelling and rifting along the Bransfield Strait. The latter is due to a slab roll-back that led to the break-up of the South Shetlands from the Antarctic Peninsula and consequent subduction termination.

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INTRODUCTION AND GEOLOGICAL BACKGROUND

The active margin of the Andean/Antarctic Peninsula is formed by several successive volcanic arc events from the Early Paleozoic to the Triassic, followed by the Jurassic back-arc rift extension that resulted in the Gondwana break-up (Jordan *et al.*, 2020). The Lower Cretaceous to Miocene South Shetland Islands volcanic arc is a result of the subduction of the Phoenix Oceanic Microplate (part of the Pacific Plate) beneath the Antarctic Peninsula (Smellie *et al.*, 1984; Kamenov, 1997, 2008; Haase *et al.*, 2012; Bastías *et al.*, 2023, and references therein). The margin segment of the South Shetland Islands is laterally limited by the Hero and Shackleton fracture zones to the southwest and northeast, respectively. The evolution of the volcanic arc resulted in the formation of various sedimentary basins and paleoenvironments (turbiditic to shallow marine and continental) that formed varied sedimentary successions and tholeiitic to potassium calc-alkaline subduction-related magmatic rocks. The volcanic arc activity peak lasted from the Early to Late Cretaceous (on Livingston Island) and to the Paleocene–Eocene on King George and Nelson islands. Following the subduction of the Phoenix Plate accretion with the continental margin of the Antarctic Peninsula in the Late Mesozoic, the subduction in the region slowed down and was followed by the Paleocene–Eocene (65–47 Ma) high-pressure to low-temperature metamorphic event recorded in the rocks cropping out on Smith and Elephant islands (Grunow *et al.*, 1992; Truow *et al.*, 1998; Hervé *et al.*, 2006a; Chen *et al.*, 2021). This compressional regime was followed by a vast regional extension that triggered the emplacement of Eocene (46–40 Ma) mafic to intermediate intrusions and dikes (Smellie *et al.*, 1984; Willan and Kelley, 1999; Kamenov *et al.*, 2005). The break-up of Patagonia and the Antarctic Peninsula and the formation of the Drake Passage is interpreted to have occurred during the interval between 50 Ma and 30 Ma, but the deepwater connection developed around 34–30 Ma, when the Antarctic Circumpolar Current formed (Livermore *et al.*, 2005; Eagles and Jokat, 2014; Bastías *et al.*, 2022, and references therein). This led to a drastic climate change and sudden widespread glaciation of Antarctica (*e.g.*, De Conto *et al.*, 2003). Late Eocene to Miocene and recent glacial and interglacial volcanism and sedimentation are well-exposed on King George Island (Birkenmajer, 1987; Warny *et al.*, 2015, 2019). The magmatism related to the volcanic arc ceased

at around 20 Ma, but earthquake activity along the South Shetland Trench is registered even nowadays (Robertson *et al.*, 2003). Subduction of the Phoenix Plate under the South Shetland Trench slowed and may have stopped at 3.3 Ma when spreading ceased on the Antarctic-Phoenix Ridge (Larter and Barker, 1991; Fretzdorf *et al.*, 2004, and references therein). The consequent slab roll-back provoked an extensional regime and asthenospheric upwelling that led to rifting, break-up of the South Shetlands from the Antarctic Peninsula and the opening of the Bransfield Strait. The latter was accompanied by Quaternary alkaline volcanism (Hole *et al.*, 1995).

Livingston Island is the second largest island of the South Shetland Archipelago. The island chain is separated from the Antarctic Peninsula by the Bransfield Strait and from South America by the Drake Passage. Late Jurassic to recent sedimentary and igneous rocks are exposed in several localities separated by the permanent ice cap. To better understand the geological evolution of the sedimentary basins and tectono-magmatic events in the area, the present review paper summarizes the published data on the geology of Livingston Island.

GEOLOGY OF THE MAIN LOCALITIES, SEDIMENTARY BASINS AND TECTONO-MAGMATIC EVENTS OF LIVINGSTON ISLAND

Simplified geological scheme of Livingston Island is given in Fig. 1. The geochronology data of the main tectono-magmatic events are generalized in Fig. 2, and the stratigraphy of the main sedimentary units is illustrated in Fig. 3. The exposed localities are presented from the north-west to the south-east as follows: Byers Peninsula; Cape Shirreff; Hannah Point; Siddons Point; Williams Point; Hurd Peninsula; Barnard Point; and Tangra Mountain.

Byers Peninsula

The Byers Peninsula occupies the north-western extremity of Livingston Island, which is also the largest ice-free area on the South Shetland Archipelago. The Byers Peninsula comprises 60 km² of essentially ice-free desolate, low-relief topography veneered by periglacial debris.

Sedimentary, igneous and volcanic rocks exposed on the Byers Peninsula are combined in the Byers Group, proposed by Crame *et al.* (1993) and revised by Hathway (1997) and Hathway and Lomas (1998). According to Hathway and Lomas (1998), the Byers Group is composed of Mesozoic sedimentary, volcano-sedimentary, volcanoclastic

Fig. 1. Geological scheme of Livingston Island (modified after Smellie *et al.*, 1984; Smellie, 1996; Hathway and Lomas, 1998; Bonev *et al.*, 2015); regional scheme (bottom right) after Bastías *et al.* (2023).

Fig. 2. Diagram of temporal evolution of the geology of Livingston Island (age data after Pankhurst *et al.*, 1979; Gracanic, 1983; Smellie *et al.*, 1984, 1996; Kamenov and Monchev, 1996; Sheng *et al.*, 1997; Kamenov, 1997; Hathway *et al.*, 1999; Oteiza, 1999; Willan and Kelly, 1999; Zheng *et al.*, 2002; Sell *et al.*, 2004; Kamenov *et al.*, 2005; Kraus *et al.*, 2007; Haase *et al.*, 2012; Bastías *et al.*, 2019).

Fig. 3. General stratigraphy of the main sedimentary successions on Livingston Island.

and igneous rocks of Late Jurassic to Early Cretaceous age. The group comprises five formations in superposition as follows: the Anchorage Formation (?Kimmeridgian–Tithonian), the President Beaches Formation (Berriasian), the Start Hill Formation (Berriasian), the Chester Cone Formation (latest Berriasian–middle Valanginian) and the Cerro Negro Formation (early Aptian).

The Anchorage Formation consists of grey to black radiolarian-rich (hemi)pelagic mudstones ac-

cumulated in deepwater paleoenvironments. It is covered by the mudstone-dominated (with sand-rich packages) President Beaches Formation, deposited in relatively deepwater, slope-apron environments (Pimpirev and Vangelov, 1998; Lomas, 1999). Based on the ammonite fauna, mainly represented by the genus *Spiticeras*, and a single specimen defined as *Argentinceras*, Dochev *et al.* (2017) suggested Late Berriasian age for the upper part of the formation. The volcanic breccias of the Start Hill Formation are interpreted as a part of marine debris apron surrounding a nearby subaerial basaltic volcano or volcanoes (Hathway and Lomas, 1998), indicating that the sedimentation was coeval with intensive arc volcanic activity from at least early Valanginian times (Lomas, 1999). The succeeding latest Berriasian–Valanginian Chester Cone Formation is composed of conglomerates, the sandstones of the Devils Point Member and the shales of the Sealer Hill Member. All these rocks were deposited in a shallow-marine environment. The Cerro Negro Formation consists of volcanoclastic rocks (pyroclastics and volcanoclastic sediments), deposited in non-marine conditions after a Valanginian–Aptian erosional hiatus (Hathway and Lomas, 1998).

The igneous rocks of the Byers Peninsula are represented by Early Cretaceous lava flows (Fig. 4a), sills, dikes, volcanic plugs, some subvolcanic to hypabyssal bodies and volcanoclastics (pyroclastic rocks and volcanoclastic sediments). The volcano-sedimentary succession contains examples of interaction between magma and wet, unconsolidated sediments resulting in peperitic contacts (Fig. 4b) and hyaloclastite formation, which show their contemporaneous formation in a shallow-water environment (Velev *et al.*, 2018, 2020). According to the latter authors, the penetration of the magma in the wet unconsolidated sediments resulted in quench fragmentation and generation of *in situ* hyaloclastite.

The geochronological data obtained from the volcanic/subvolcanic rocks fall in several time intervals between the Early Jurassic and the Early Cretaceous. A distal tuff layer in the upper section of the Anchorage Formation is dated at 153.1±1.7 Ma (Late Jurassic). Based on ⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar dating, Haase *et al.* (2012) suggested Valanginian age (135.2±2.6 Ma) for the aphyric lavas from the Start Hill Formation. Pankhurst *et al.* (1979) reported K-Ar amphibole age of 132±4 Ma for an andesite plug of the Chester Cone Formation. There are several ages of silicic volcanoclastic rocks from the Cerro Negro Formation. The ⁴⁰Ar/³⁹Ar analysis of plagioclase from a basal tuff yielded an age of 120.3±2.2 Ma

Fig. 4. Field photographs of some of the geology features on Livingston Island: a) lava flow with lower colonnade and entablature at the Byers Peninsula; b) peperite contacts between lava and unconsolidated wet sediments at the Byers Peninsula; c) volcanic succession crosscut by two dikes at Hannah Point; d) turbidites of the Miers Bluff Formation; e) volcanic neck of Nunatak de Castillo; f) dikes at the Hurd Peninsula; g) dike at Sally Rocks, Hurd Peninsula; h) sill that crosscuts sediments of the Miers Bluff Formation and quartz veins at the Hurd Peninsula; i) Pico Moores and Cerro Mirador Eocene intrusions; j) granodiorite with mafic enclave at Cerro Mirador; k) quartz vein with copper oxidation; l) Eocene Barnard Point batholith and Tangra Mountain; m) mingling mafic enclaves in the Barnard Point granodiorite; n) mineralization with bornite, chalcopyrite and molybdenite at Barnard Point.

(Hathway, 1997; Hathway *et al.*, 1999). Ignimbritic clasts in a conglomerate unit below the top of the succession yielded $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ ages of 119.4 ± 0.6 Ma and 119.1 ± 0.8 Ma on biotite and plagioclase (Hathway *et al.*, 1999). The Cerro Negro plug is dated at 111 Ma using Rb-Sr method (Smellie, 1984). Sealer plug is dated at 111 ± 5 Ma using Ar-Ar method (Gracanic, 1983). These may represent the last intrusive cross-cutting event in the Byers Peninsula. Several younger K-Ar ages have been reported from the upper part of the Cerro Negro Formation including the intrusive rocks at Negro Hill. All these younger ages range from ca. 95 Ma to ca. 76 Ma (Pankhurs *et al.*, 1979, 1984; Oteiza, 1999) and most probably represent Ar loss.

Cape Shirreff

Cape Shirreff represents a promontory at the north end of Livingston Island. The olivine basalt sills of Cape Shirreff (Smellie, 1996) are dated using K-Ar at 90.2 ± 5.6 Ma.

Hannah Point

Geographically, Hannah Point is situated on the south-central coast of Livingston Island between the Hurd Peninsula and the Byers Peninsula.

According to the rock types and the contacts between the units, Pallàs *et al.* (1999) divided the stratigraphic succession of Hannah Point into five informal lithostratigraphic units (from A to E). Unit A (120 m) is mainly composed of polymict volcanoclastic breccias and dacitic lava flows. Unit B (70 m) is dominated by volcanic breccias and rare volcanoclastic conglomerate layers. Unit C (65 m) is mainly composed of basaltic lavas and minor volcanoclastic breccias. Unit D (65 m) consists of alternating polymict clast- and matrix-supported breccias and volcanoclastic conglomerate layers. Unit E (150 m) is composed of thick andesitic lava layers.

According to Velev *et al.* (2020), the Upper Cretaceous volcano-sedimentary succession at Hannah Point is composed of lava flows, dikes, volcanic plugs, pyroclastic and epiclastic rocks and rare thin beds of sediments. The lower part of the succession is partly occupied by two lava flows, which are separated by autoclastic lava breccia. Typical for the flows are colonnade and entablature structures. Two other lava flows occupy the middle parts of the succession. The volcanoclastic rocks are presented by epiclastics and pyroclastics (agglomerate tuffs and ignimbrites). One volcanic plug (reconstructed from

the orientation of the columnar jointing) is intruded in volcano-sedimentary layers in the northern part of the cross section and represent a typical remnant of an eroded volcanic vent. The volcano-sedimentary succession is crosscut by two dikes that represent the last intrusive episode (Fig. 4c).

The fossil flora (leaf imprints) obtained from Unit E (Leppe *et al.*, 2007) gave a Late Cretaceous (Coniacian–Santonian) age.

The rocks from Hannah Point were considered as a part of the Lower Cretaceous volcanic sequences of the Byers Peninsula (Smellie *et al.*, 1984). Subsequent K-Ar analyses of two basaltic andesite samples, corresponding to the middle part of the succession, gave 87.9 ± 2.6 Ma indicating that they are Late Cretaceous in age (Smellie *et al.*, 1996). The younger age of 67.5 ± 2.5 Ma from the upper basaltic andesite lava flow is assumed by the latter authors to have been rejuvenated due to Ar-loss. Slightly older ages were obtained by Haase *et al.* (2012) based on $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ whole rock data giving an age of 97.5 Ma. The Late Cretaceous volcanic succession at Hannah Point contains secondary mineral associations characteristic for very low-grade metamorphism (Bastias *et al.*, 2016). The minerals occur in fractures (veins and veinlets), amygdules, groundmass/matrix and phenocrysts.

Siddons Point

Siddons Point is situated at the middle of Hero Bay along the north coast of Livingston Island. The dolerite sill at Siddons Point, dated at 73 ± 2.3 Ma, probably belongs to the Late Cretaceous episode of intrusion associated with the Coppermine Formation (Smellie *et al.*, 1996).

Williams Point

Williams Point is the north-easternmost extremity of Livingston Island. At Williams Point, several small hydroclastic vents and sills (20–50 m) intrude a gently dipping, weakly lithified sequence known as Williams Point Beds (Hobbs, 1968; Smellie *et al.*, 1984). The sills and vents yielded K-Ar ages between 81 Ma and 74 Ma. The Williams Point Beds comprise a crudely upward-thinning and fining sequence, about 80–90 m thick. It commences as thick, massive conglomerates and phase-up trough cross-stratified sandstones with thin conglomerates into a sequence of vitric lapilli-tuffs and mudstones. Previous collection of floral remains from the Williams Point Beds were reported to represent a terrestrial sedimentary sequence with Triassic age

(e.g., Lacey and Lucas, 1981). The last studies of the fossil flora, however, prove Cretaceous (Albian–Cenomanian) age of the sediments (Rees and Smellie, 1989).

Hurd Peninsula

The Hurd Peninsula is situated at the eastern part of Livingston Island and hosts the Bulgarian Antarctic Base “St. Kliment Ohridski” and the Spanish Antarctic Base “Juan Carlos”. The rock formations on the Hurd Peninsula are represented by sedimentary and volcano-sedimentary successions and numerous generations of dikes and small intrusions and the Hesperides pluton. The sedimentary and volcano-sedimentary successions are grouped in two major lithostratigraphic units: the Miers Bluff Formation (composed of sedimentary sequences) and the Mount Bowless Formation (composed of volcano-sedimentary rocks).

The Miers Bluff Formation (Dalzel, 1972) was initially divided into three informal lithostratigraphic units, namely U1, U2 and U3 (Pallas *et al.*, 1992). Later, the Miers Bluff Formation (Fig. 4d) was revised by Smellie *et al.* (1995) and subdivided into the following units: 1) the Johnsons Dock Member (coarse- to fine-grained turbidites); 2) the Napier Peak Breccias (mudstone-dominated breccias, intercalated by mudstone packages); and 3) the Moores Peak Member (massive breccias with sandstone and mudstone clasts). The latter was introduced by Pimpirev *et al.* (2000, fig. 2, IIIb). Doktor *et al.* (1994) introduced the South Bay Member (amalgamated massive sandstones alternating with thick mudstones and fine-grained sandstones). Recently, Pimpirev *et al.* (2015) introduced the Sally Rock Member (thin-bedded alternation of mudstones and sandstones). The sediments have undergone anchizonal regional metamorphism (Smellie *et al.*, 1995). The depositional age of the formation was poorly constrained and Schopf (1973) initially proposed an age younger than Carboniferous. The dating of detrital zircons from turbiditic sandstones showed a wide temporal interval of the supplying provenance ages, spanning the interval between the Late Carboniferous and the Early–Middle Jurassic, with a maximum deposition age of about 170 Ma (Hervé *et al.*, 2006). Shu *et al.* (2000) reported poorly preserved palynoflora and proposed a Triassic age. Pimpirev *et al.* (2006) suggested that the lowermost part of the sedimentary succession is not exposed on the surface, based on abundant scattered blocks of black silty mudstone on the marine terrace of the Bulgarian Beach that often contain poorly preserved belemnites, bivalves

and single ammonites. Based on a single specimen defined as *Blandfordiceras* sp. aff. *wallichii*, a late Tithonian age was proposed for the probable lowermost, unexposed part of the Miers Bluff Formation (Pimpirev *et al.*, 2002). Based on calcareous nannofossil data obtained from all members, a Campanian–Maastrichtian age for the Miers Bluff Formation has been proven (Stoykova *et al.*, 2002; Pimpirev *et al.*, 2006a, b).

The lower and middle parts of the sedimentary sequences of the Miers Bluff Formation (Campanian–Maastrichtian) were formed in a deep-marine paleoenvironment (Stefanov and Pimpirev, 2015), while the upper part of the formation (Maastrichtian–?Paleocene) represents the final regressive stage with coarse sedimentation.

Volcanic rocks metamorphosed at subgreenschist facies conditions are exposed on the southeastern part of the Hurd Peninsula and the central Livingston Island. These were nominated as the Mount Bowless Formation (Smellie *et al.*, 1995). According to Kamenov (2011), the predominant parts of the isolated exposures are coarse-grained lapillis-tuffs, interbedded with lava flows and sedimentary rocks. A probable volcanic neck is located at Nunatak de Castillo (Bonev *et al.*, 2015; Fig. 4e). Typical sections crop out west of Willan Nunatak and in the southern part of Mount Bowless. Here, different lava varieties occur more often. The volcanoclastic rocks predominate the southern area of Burdick Peak, where these rocks overlie unconformably the beds of the Miers Bluff Formation. The relationships between the isolated exposures are unclear, due to their fragmentary character and the great variety of the bedding orientation. It is difficult to assess the age of the rocks due to the metamorphic overprint. They are usually dated in the interval of 48–35 Ma using K-Ar, but that is most probably due to Ar-loss (Smellie *et al.*, 1996). The assemblages of the secondary minerals in the volcanic rocks were a result of contact metamorphism (Smellie *et al.*, 1995), or they are products of hydrothermal local metamorphism (Willan, 1994). Two Ar-Ar isochron geochronology ages of basalts at 110–105 Ma (Zheng *et al.*, 1997) gave a clue for their possible Late Cretaceous age. Nevertheless, these rocks overlie unconformably the Campanian–Maastrichtian strata of the Miers Bluff Formation, hence they should be younger. Kamenov (2011) proved that the low-grade metamorphic event (1.1 kbar and temperature of 278 °C) is most probably due to Andean type of burial metamorphism.

In the Hurd Peninsula, several generations of mafic to intermediate dikes (Fig. 4f–h) crosscut the sedimentary succession of the Miers Bluff Formation and volcano-sedimentary rocks of the Mount Bowless Formation. Based on their field relationships and age determinations, they can be divided into different generations. Most of the K-Ar and Ar-Ar ages are in the range of 79–31 Ma (Willan and Kelley, 1999; Zheng *et al.*, 2002; Kraus *et al.*, 2007; Kamenov, 2015, and references therein). Using their field relationships, the dike emplacement history is divided into four episodes (Zheng *et al.*, 2002). The Late Cretaceous–Paleocene dikes in the range of 80–60 Ma are related to the main magmatism on Livingston Island and most likely reflect the final stages of subduction of the proto-Pacific oceanic crust. The early Eocene dikes (56–52 Ma) fill the gap in volcanic activity 70–50 Ma ago, and thus represent the only magmatic event at this time in the region. The 45–42 Ma dikes may be related to the intrusion of the Barnard Point tonalite (Kamenov, 2015, and references therein). The final Oligocene age appears to represent the last igneous activities on the Hurd Peninsula prior to the opening of the Bransfield Strait (Willan and Kelly, 1999; Zheng *et al.*, 2002).

The Hesperides pluton crops out along the northernmost part of the west coast of the Hurd Peninsula (Kamenov, 2015). The pluton is a small and well-exposed stock intruded in the sediments of the Campanian–Maastrichtian Miers Bluff Formation. The contacts are sharp and magmatic, and the intrusion hosts a large number of sedimentary xenoliths from the host formations. The Hesperides magmatic body consists of gabbro, diorite and quartz-diorite (Kamenov *et al.*, 2015). The SHRIMP zircon U-Pb age is dated at 137.7 ± 1.4 Ma (Hervé *et al.*, 2006), but most probably represents a xeno-crystal component. The age of 73 ± 3 Ma (Kamenov, 1997) obtained by K-Ar method is accepted as the age of emplacement and magma crystallization.

Several small plutonic bodies are exposed on the eastern side of the Hurd Peninsula, and thus show a spatial relation to the Eocene Barnard Point batholith (Smellie, 1984; Kamenov *et al.*, 2005). The petrographic, geochemical, Ar-Ar and K-Ar geochronology studies (Smellie, 1996; Kamenov *et al.*, 2005) on the stocks exposed (Fig. 4i, j) at Moores Peak (diorite, 43.43 ± 0.86 Ma), Cerro Mirador (granodiorite, 42.5–40 Ma) and Willan Nunatak (43–41 Ma) reveal that the main rock varieties are diorite, quartz-diorite and granodiorite, similar

to those of the batholith and similar to some of the dikes in the Hurd Peninsula.

Numerous epithermal quartz-base metal veins (Fig. 4k) are hosted in the sediments of the Miers Bluff Formation and some of the dikes on the Hurd Peninsula (Willan, 1994; Willan and Kelly, 1999; Velev *et al.*, 2016; Sabeva *et al.*, 2020a, b; Sabeva and Velev, 2022). According to Sabeva and Velev (2022), the epithermal veins consist of chalcopyrite, sphalerite, galena, pyrite and arsenopyrite. Chalcopyrite and sphalerite predominate, galena is second in distribution, and pyrite and arsenopyrite are subordinate. Potassium feldspar obtained from one of the veins gives K-Ar concordant isochron age of 42.3 ± 0.7 Ma (Willan and Kelly, 1999). However, the latter authors report that some of the veins are cut by dikes with 74 Ma and 51–45 Ma Ar-Ar ages, so it is assumed that the 42–37 Ma age cluster from K-feldspars of the veins can be related to Ar loss (*ibid.*).

Barnard Point batholith and Tangra Mountain area

Barnard Point is situated in the south-eastern coast of the entrance of False Bay, where Eocene plutonic bodies are exposed and represented by the Barnard Point batholith (Smellie *et al.*, 1984; Willan and Kelly, 1999; Kamenov, 2015; Velev *et al.*, 2022). The batholith (Fig. 4l) comprises most of the Tangra Mountain ridge and consists of gabbro, pegmatoid gabbro, intruded by granodiorite with mafic mingling enclaves (Fig. 4m) and dikes, but is also cut by later mafic dikes (Willan and Kelly, 1999). A deeply eroded porphyry-copper system (Fig. 4n) with pegmatite veins is reported by Armstrong and Willan (1995). The geochronology of the granodiorite/tonalite by Rb-Sr (Smellie *et al.*, 1984) and K-Ar (Willan and Kelly, 1999) is in the interval 46–40 Ma. The pluton is cut by mafic to intermediate in composition dikes at 35–29 Ma (Willan and Kelly, 1999). According to the latter authors, the porphyry-copper system is related to the Eocene granodiorite, but the K-Ar dating of biotite from pegmatite veins coeval with the porphyry system gives an age of 29.3 ± 0.7 Ma. The younger age is interpreted to be reset by the last episode of dike intrusion. Carbonate/sericite veins, dated at 32.3 ± 0.3 Ma, are associated with the last dikes.

The apatite FT low-temperature geochronology of rocks from Livingston Island (Sell *et al.*, 2000, 2004) showed that the metasediments and

the Miers Bluff Formation (Hurd Peninsula) were reheated by the last magmatic event on the island during the Oligocene (~25.8 Ma). The apatite FT ages of the Barnard Point pluton are early to mid-Miocene (22–16 Ma).

The youngest volcanic rocks on Livingston Island form the Inott Point Formation and crop out at its northeastern end next to Burdik Peak (Hoobs, 1968; Smellie *et al.*, 1984). They consist of Pliocene to recent alkaline and tholeiitic basaltic lavas and pyroclastic lavas (Veit, 2002; Kamenov, 2004, 2015). This magmatic event corresponds to the magmatism related to the Bransfield Rift and the closest active volcanic center is Deception volcano. The outcrops with Quaternary volcanic rocks on Livingston Island are aligned parallel to the Bransfield Strait structure.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The magmatic activity on Livingston Island took place in a long interval from the Early Cretaceous to present. The age migration of the magmatic activity in the South Shetland arc has been a matter of large debates. A geographic trend of decreasing age of the volcanism from south-west to north-east along the arc (parallel to the trench) was recognized by Smellie *et al.* (1984) and was attributed to the rotation of the Antarctic Plate (Birkenmajer, 1995). Haase *et al.* (2012) suggested that the volcanic migration proceeded in a series of major steps, rather than a progressive north-eastern migration. However, considering the magmatic activity on Livingston Island, a general trend of rejuvenation is visible from the WNW (Byers Peninsula) to the ESE (to Hannah Point, Point Williams, further to the Hurd Peninsula and the Tangra Mountain). This trend generally propagates from the subduction trench in the direction of the upper plate. The rejuvenation of the magmatic rocks in the direction of the thrust plate can be explained as an effect of a flattening subduction active from the Early Cretaceous (135 Ma) up to around 90–70 Ma. However, there is an area on the island (in the Hurd Peninsula for example) where a strict age migration cannot be found. Here, dikes and small plutonic bodies with crosscutting relationships were intruded in several episodes/generations between 80 Ma and 31 Ma (Kamenov, 2015, and references therein). These could be related to periods of rotation and probably beginning of a slab roll-back that caused extension at the time interval of 50–30 Ma and culminating with the opening of the Drake Pas-

sage around 34–30 Ma (Livermore *et al.*, 2005). Regionally, this episode is preceded by the high-pressure low-temperature metamorphism of the rocks from Smith Island (Trouw *et al.*, 1998) and was possibly also recorded by their exhumation. By that time, the large Eocene Barnard Point pluton (46–40 Ma) was already emplaced and the last magmatic episode is recorded by the presence of dikes dated at ca. 30 Ma. The burial metamorphism (Kamenov, 2011) that caused major Ar-loss in the Mount Bowles Formation most probably preceded the extensional event. The major phase of uplift of the Tangra Mountain happened around 22–16 Ma as indicated by the Ap FT thermochronology (Sell *et al.*, 2004). Due to the Miocene exhumation, the different hydrothermal systems reported, even still not proven as genetically related and coeval to each other, remain in different structural/erosion levels. For example, the deeply eroded porphyry-copper system reported for the Barnard Point area (Armstrong *et al.*, 1996) and the shallower epithermal one on the Hurd Peninsula (*e.g.*, Willan, 1994; Sabeva and Velev, 2022). The last magmatic event on the island produced the contrastingly different in composition Quaternary alkaline mafic rocks between Innot Point and Burdick (Rezen Peak locality). They could be referred to the magmatism of the Bransfield Strait Rift and considered as a parallel crypto-rift structure. This episode is interpreted as related to the extension that culminated in asthenospheric upwelling and rifting along the Bransfield Strait due to the processes of a slab roll-back (Hole *et al.*, 1995). These led to the break-up of the South Shetlands from the Antarctic Peninsula and subduction termination.

During the geological evolution of Livingston Island, the paleoenvironmental basin settings also changed from the WNW to the ESE, which led to various depositional conditions for the formed sedimentary successions. At the western part of the Byers Peninsula, the ?Kimmeridgian–Berriasian sediments were deposited in deep-marine paleoenvironments, while in the central part of the peninsula ?Berriasian–Valanginian sediments were deposited under shallow-marine conditions. In the eastern part of the Byers Peninsula, Valanginian–Aptian sedimentary rocks are deposited in non-marine conditions (Hathway and Lomas, 1998; Lomas, 1999). The sedimentary beds exposed in the central part of the island (Hannah Point) are non-marine also and younger (Coniacian–Santonian). Along with this, the paleovolcanic settings changed from subaqueous-subaerial at the most WNW part (Byers Peninsula) to subaerial at the central parts of the island (Hannah Point).

At the eastern part of the island (Hurd Peninsula), the lower and middle part of the anchimetamorphosed sedimentary sequences of the Miers Bluff Formation (Campanian–Maastrichtian) are also formed in deep marine paleoenvironments, while the upper part of the formation (Maastrichtian–Paleocene) demonstrated the final regressive stage with coarse sedimentation (Stefanov and Pimpirev, 2015).

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